

from the Arctic Circle to the high mountains of warm temperate regions¹. Literature survey showed that no work has been reported on this plant.

Experimental

The leaves of *Picea morinda* (1 kg) collected from Dehra-Dun, were extracted with hot ethanol and ethanolic concentrate was left in a refrigerator, when a greenish solid mass settled (5 g). It was filtered and washed with petroleum ether, benzene and chloroform. The purified yellow product gave positive tests for flavonoids and showed two brown spots on tlc (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36:9:5)² corresponding to R_f values of amentoflavone and its monomethyl ether. These were separated by preparative tlc (silica gel G) and labelled as PM (2 g) and PMI (4 mg) in order of increasing R_f values.

PMI, m.p. 218-19° was the minor component and characterised as 5,7-dihydroxyflavone by uv studies, λ_{max} (MeOH) 268, 334 nm + AlCl₃, 275, 384 (sh) nm + NaOAc 284, 338. It gave usual flavonoidic tests.

The chromatographically homogeneous fraction PM on methylation [(CH₃)₂SO₄-K₂CO₃] and tlc examination was found to be a mixture of three biflavones. These were separated by tlc (B-P-F), crystallised from CHCl₃, labelled as PMA, PMB, and PMC, and identified as hexa-*O*-methyl ethers of amentoflavone³, cupressuflavone⁴ and agathisflavone⁵, respectively. PM on acetylation with Ac₂O-Py, followed by fractional crystallisation with CHCl₃-MeOH gave two compounds, characterised as hexa-*O*-acetates of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone, respectively. The structures of all compounds were established by comparing the ¹H nmr data of their methyl ethers and acetates with those of authentic samples. However, the third component could not be purified by fractional crystallisations but presumed to be agathisflavone hexaacetate.

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Free Amino Acids of *Melastoma melabathricum*

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MELASTOMA melabathricum Linn.¹ (*Melastomataceae*) is a shrub of variable heights from 3 to 8 ft with bright pinkish flowers in the hilly areas as well as in the lower level lands of Tripura, Assam and Bangladesh. The leaves, flowers and fruits can be eaten. The plant is said to be useful in cholera, diarrhoea, prolonged fever, dysentery, leucorrhoea, healing wounds, skin diseases and for the preparation of gargles². Previous investigations revealed the presence of a purple dyestuff, β -sitosterol and melastomic acid (triterpene) in the roots^{2,3}, and aliphatic compounds in the aerial parts⁴ of the plant. To find out the diet value of the leaves in respect to amino acid content, we investigated chemically the leaves of the plant and isolated eleven amino acids among which five being essential. In the present communication, we report the isolation, identification and relative occurrence of these amino acids in leaves.

The leaves of the plant, *M. melabathricum* L. were collected from the tilla areas of Agartala in May, 1984. The air-dried leaves (500 g) were milled and extracted in a Soxhlet with petrol (b.p. 60-80°) and 90% ethanol successively for 48 h each. The alcoholic extract was concentrated and decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal. The brown filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to a gummy residue (19.2 g). The residue (1 g) was demineralised in the usual procedure^{5,6} by passing through a column of Amberlite IR 120 (H). The column was washed with water (70 ml) till the eluate gave negative test with Molisch reagent for carbohydrates. The amino acids were then eluted with 5% NH₄OH solution. The elution was continued till a drop of eluate failed to give bluish violet colouration on a filter paper moistened with ninhydrin reagent (0.20% in acetone). The total eluate was concentrated under reduced pressure and paper chromatographed in descending technique on Whatman No. 1 in two directions⁷ using solvent system n-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O (12:3:5; solvent I) in one direction and PhOH-H₂O-NH₄OH (5:1.25:0.9; solvent II) in the other direction. Amino acids were located on chromatogram by spraying ninhydrin reagent and heating the paper at 100° for a few minutes. R_f values of amino acids were measured and compared with those of authentic samples. The amino acids were then identified as glycine, valine, leucine, isoleucine, methionine, tyrosine, hydroxyproline aspartic acid and glutamic acid by co-pc with authentic samples.

Another 1.0 g of the crude residue was also desalted by resin chromatography through Amberlite IRA 400 (OH) as before. The amino acids were eluted with 1 N acetic acid. The eluate was concentrated under reduced pressure and paper chromatographed in solvents I and II. Two amino acids found were identified as arginine and serine by co-pc with authentic samples.

All these amino acids from their mixture were isolated as individual ninhydrin complexes by preparative pc⁸ on Whatmann 3 mm using solvent-I as developing solvent and ninhydrin as spray reagent and heating the chromatogram at 100°. The colour bands were mapped out by pencil and R_f of each coloured band was compared with the R_f of authentic sample. Each band was cut out in small strips and the strips were moistened with 75% ethanol (10 ml) in petri dish for 0.5 h. The strips were then removed by thorough washing with 75% ethanol. The solution in the petri dish was transferred to a colorimeter tube and ninhydrin reagent (1 ml) (to ensure completion of reaction) added to it and warmed the mixture for 15 min. The coloured solution was cooled to room temperature, the volume was made up to 10 ml with 75% ethanol and optical density (O.D.) was measured colorimetrically⁹ at 540 nm by a VIS Bausch & Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. The amount of each amino acid was obtained by interpolation of its O.D. in the standard O.D. vs concentration curve of authentic sample. The O.D. at different concentrations of the authentic sample were measured by adding 2 ml of reagent to 8 ml of solution in 75% alcohol and the resultant solution warmed on steam-bath for 15 min and finally the volume of the solution made up to 10 ml. For yellow coloured solution of hydroxyproline, O.D. was measured⁷ at 440 nm.

The relative occurrence of individual amino acids in µg per g of air-dried leaves, was found to be arginine, 98.0; tyrosine, 69.0; hydroxy proline, 32.9; valine, 16.0; serine, 16.0; glutamic acid, 15.3; methionine, 9.2; isoleucine, 7.8; aspartic acid, 6.7; leucine, 5.3 and glycine, 2.8. Among these, arginine, valine, methionine, leucine and isoleucine are essential amino acids.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Microgram Amounts of Rhodium(III) with Methotrimeprazine †

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IN continuation of our studies on *N*-alkylphenothiazines as analytical reagents¹⁻³, we have examined the reaction between rhodium(III) and methotrimeprazine (MTM) and proposed MTM as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III). The method is elegant, sensitive, simple and offers unique advantage of the determination of rhodium in the presence of iridium.

Experimental

A stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving rhodium(III) chloride (0.8368 g) in 1 M hydrochloric acid (250 ml). It was standardised gravimetrically by precipitating rhodium as the sulphide, followed by ignition to the oxide and then reduction to the metal in presence of hydrogen⁴. A 0.2% aqueous solution of methotrimeprazine was prepared and stored in a refrigerator. Walpole buffers in the pH range 0.65-5.20 were prepared from 1 M sodium acetate (AnalaR) and 1 M hydrochloric acid (AnalaR) solutions. Aqueous solutions of 2% ascorbic acid and 0.05 M copper(II) sulphate were prepared from analytical grade reagents. Compounds of acceptable grades of purity were used in preparing other solutions used in interference studies.

Absorbance measurements were carried out on a Beckman DB spectrophotometer equipped with matched 1.0 cm glass cells, and pH measurements were made with a Elico L 1-120 digital pH meter.

Procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing up to 525 µg of rhodium(III) was transferred

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